

First benchmark of the EU carbon and climate methodologies/tools

M6/March 2023

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**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060212.

Project Full Title	A EUROPEAN-WIDE NETWORK OF PILOT FARMERS IMPLEMENTING AND DEMONSTRATING CLIMATE SMART SOLUTIONS FOR A CARBON NEUTRAL EUROPE
GA number	101060212
Type of Action	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Project Duration	84 months
Project Start Date	01.10.2022.
Project Website	TBC
Milestone Title	First benchmark of the EU carbon and climate methodologies/tools
Milestone Submission Date	31.03.2023.
Status	Final
Milestone Lead organisation	AUA
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Work Package	WP 5

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Means of Verification

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Introduction

The Climate Farm Demo project's WP5 aims to develop a digital repository for carbon and environmental models, methods and tools that have been widely used and implemented across the EU for climate change mitigation and adaptation. The repository will span across the entire agricultural sector, covering all crop, livestock and mixed production systems while also accounting for inherent differences between the highly variable pedoclimatic zones of Europe. To this end, the first task of WP5, namely Task 5.1 "Inventory/mapping of the existing carbon and climate methodologies/tools used in the EU" launched an online survey for National Coordinators (NCs) in February (M5), which successfully collected 51 replies from NCs across the EU. The objective was to obtain "current state" information and conduct a benchmark analysis of all tools/methods used across the continent and throughout various agricultural systems within the sector. The data from the replies will ultimately form the basis and initial entries for the online repository that will be created by AUA (M18).

The online survey can be accessed in the link:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdIJGAWYxDORjPyxHox1AKIf11K9gz2u9WAiBPLtFxSCbJNwA/viewform>

The exported results have been archived to the online Teams page of the project (access might be limited outside project partners):

[https://actaassofr.sharepoint.com/:x/r/sites/h-eu/Documents%20partages/GeneralWork%20Packages/f.%20WP5/Task%205.1/Survey%20WP5%20\(Exported,%20Uncurated\).csv?d=weac65addab754fd7b90c92ed5da29fc1&csf=1&web=1&e=M3k3ui](https://actaassofr.sharepoint.com/:x/r/sites/h-eu/Documents%20partages/GeneralWork%20Packages/f.%20WP5/Task%205.1/Survey%20WP5%20(Exported,%20Uncurated).csv?d=weac65addab754fd7b90c92ed5da29fc1&csf=1&web=1&e=M3k3ui)

Results Overview

This Milestone document is accompanied by a short report in the form of visualised obtained results, with the main findings being presented in the present section. Certain questions of importance have been selected to be included, to provide a general overview of the Methods and Tools across the EU.

A breakdown of all tools collected in the survey is presented in Figure 1. The most widely used tool across NCs was the French tool CAP2ER, while over 30 replies provided a unique entry, demonstrating a highly versatile field where farmers can access numerous tools based on their various needs and objectives.

Figure 1. The replies from the first question, "What is the name of the tool?".

Another highly heterogeneous field was the agricultural system of implementation, with representation from all 11 farm systems (Figure 2). Dairy farms, crop production and cattle (beef) farms were the most common ones, accounting for almost 50% of all replies.

Farm Types Assessed

Figure 2. The replies regarding the farm type of implementation.

The question regarding the format of the tool indicated that online tools are generally more popular, accounting almost 69%, followed by computation spreadsheets and finally offline software that are used locally (Figure 3).

Type of format

Figure 3. The breakdown of the tool types.

For the main target audience of the tool, the majority (almost 80%) of them appear to focus on individual farmers, followed by tools designed for agricultural advisors (Figure 4). The low representation of scientific/experimental tools was an expectable result, given their complexity and target groups of this survey being non-academic.

Figure 4. The main target groups of the tools of this survey.

Payment fees also demonstrated variability, with the most popular ones being either open-access tools, followed by tailor-made fees based on each user (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The payment models of the tools.

A critical parameter for the objectives of Task 5.1 is language availability of the tools. To this end, an initial check was performed on whether the tool is available in English. Afterwards, the tools that were only available on local languages were categorised based on their language, with the majority of “local” replies being French, as presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The language availability of the tools.

The options of data export were also requested, with most tools naturally having a feature that allows users to freely retrieve their data. The majority of the tools allows users to freely acquire their data, while only 12% of the replies indicated that the tools restrict the export of data by the users (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The users' ability to retrieve their data locally.

Finally, one of the most important parameters for Task 5.1 and the repository that will be built is the modelled or calculated parameter. To this end, the majority (almost 82%) of the replies indicated that the tools were used for the estimation of GHG emissions rather than any other climate indicator or parameter (Figure 8).

Main calculations & results

Figure 8. The calculated/modelled parameter of the tools.

Conclusions

Based on the findings presented in this report, it is evident that there is a wide range of tools being used across the EU agricultural sector to estimate carbon and climate indicators. The results demonstrate a diverse field, with a variety of tools available to meet the specific needs of different user groups. The existence of multiple climate-focused online tools, both open-access and under payment, indicates a growing trend towards more accessible and affordable tools for users, as well as a potentially high level of acceptance towards smart climate farming practices. The availability of tools in local languages is an important consideration for ensuring their widespread use and impact. Overall, the findings of this survey provide valuable insights into the current state of carbon and climate estimation tools in the EU, information that will facilitate the initial development of the repository of CFD's WP5 Task 5.1.

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